

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

CT-TreeFlow: A Probabilistic Tree-Based Framework for Robust Groundwater Potential Mapping and Uncertainty Quantification

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Figure S1. Regional stratigraphic framework of the Zagros Basin illustrating the main lithostratigraphic units from the Cambrian to Quaternary across Lurestan, Khuzestan, Coastal Fars, and Interior Fars structural domains. The column highlights the distribution of major sedimentary formations and lithological groups (limestone, dolomite, sandstone, shale, evaporite, and salt) that constitute the hydrostratigraphic architecture of the Zagros region. Carbonate formations such as the Asmari, Sarvak, and Ilam units represent important regional aquifers, whereas

evaporitic and marly formations (e.g., Gachsaran and Gurpi) commonly act as aquitards that influence groundwater confinement and vertical flow. Modified from Ghorbani et al. (2019).

Data domain	Spatial dataset	Data type	Spatial resolution / scale	Data source	GIS-derived environmental predictors (30 m grid)
Terrain morphology	Copernicus Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	Raster	30 m	Copernicus Programme	Elevation ¹ , Slope ¹ , Aspect ¹ , Topographic Position Index (TPI) ² , Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) ³ , Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI) ⁴ , Relief Energy ⁵ , Heat Load Index (HLI) ⁶
Geological framework	Lithological units	Polygon vector	1:250,000	GSI (2022)	Lithological susceptibility to karstification ⁷
	Stratigraphic features	Point vector	1:250,000	GSI (2022)	—
	Faults and joints	Line vector	1:250,000	GSI (2022)	Fracture density ⁸ , Distance to tectonic structures ⁹
Surface hydrology	River and stream network	Line vector	1:30,000	MOE-WRMC (2024)	Drainage density ¹⁰ , Distance to surface watercourses ¹¹
Land surface characteristics	Land cover map	Polygon vector	1:30,000	ISA (2024)	Land cover classes ¹²
	Landsat-9 imagery	Raster	30 m	USGS Earth Explorer	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) ¹³
Climatic conditions	Rainfall and temperature records	Point vector	1:10,000	IMO (2024)	Spatially interpolated precipitation ¹⁴ , temperature ¹⁴
	Evapotranspiration	Raster	1:10,000	ISWRI (2024)	Evapotranspiration ¹⁵
Hydrogeological indicators	Wells inventory	Point vector	1:30,000	MOE-WRMC (2024)	Groundwater table depth ¹⁶
	Karst springs	Point vector	1:30,000	MOE-WRMC (2024)	Spring density ¹⁷
Speleological features	Known cave entrances	Point vector	1:100,000	INIOAS (2023); Ralisi & Laumanns (2003, 2009)	Spatial distribution of karst conduits ¹⁸

¹ Derived from the Copernicus DEM using standard terrain analysis procedures.

² Topographic Position Index computed using a moving window approach.

³ Topographic Wetness Index calculated following the Beven–Kirkby formulation.

⁴ Terrain Ruggedness Index derived from local elevation variability.

⁵ Relief energy calculated as the difference between maximum and minimum elevation within a defined neighborhood.

⁶ Heat Load Index computed based on terrain orientation and slope configuration.

⁷ Lithological units classified according to their relative susceptibility to karstification.

⁸ Fracture density estimated using kernel density analysis.

⁹ Euclidean distance to mapped tectonic structures.

¹⁰ Drainage density derived from the stream network.

¹¹ Distance to surface watercourses calculated using distance accumulation analysis.

¹² Land cover reclassified into hydrologically meaningful categories.

¹³ NDVI computed from Landsat-9 spectral bands.

¹⁴ Climatic variables spatially interpolated from meteorological station data.

¹⁵ Evapotranspiration obtained from raster-based datasets.

¹⁶ Groundwater table depth interpolated from well data.

¹⁷ Spring density estimated using kernel density analysis.

¹⁸ Spatial distribution of documented karst cave entrances.

Supplementary Table S1. Summary of the geospatial database compiled for groundwater potential modelling. The table lists the environmental datasets used in the study, including their data types, spatial resolution or scale, source institutions, and the derived raster conditioning factors employed as predictor variables in the machine-learning models. These datasets represent the topographic, geological, hydrological, climatic, hydrogeological, and speleological conditions controlling groundwater occurrence within the study area.

Supplementary Figure S2. Spatial distribution maps of the input conditioning factors used in the groundwater potential modelling (from Pourmorad et al., 2026). The layers include: (1) Distance from watercourses, (2) Topographic Roughness Index (TRI), (3) Evapotranspiration, (4) Topographic Position Index (TPI), (5) Relief energy, (6) Land cover, (7) Aspect, (8) Heat Load Index (HLI), (9) Temperature; (10) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), (11) Drainage Density, (12) Fracture Density, and (13) Lithology (The mapped formations include Quaternary alluvial, fluvial, deltaic, aeolian, and fan deposits (Q units), Pliocene–Miocene conglomerates and siliclastic successions of the Bakhtiari and Aghajari formations (PIQb, Mpl₁–Mpl₂), Miocene evaporitic and marl–limestone alternations of the Gachsaran and Mishan formations (Mg, Mgl, Msh), and Oligocene–Miocene carbonates of the Asmari Group (OMa, OMa–Esh, OMa–Ej, OMa–Pl). Older stratigraphic units represented include the Jahrum, Shahbazan, and Kashkan formations of Eocene age (Ej, Esh, Ek, Et), the Cretaceous carbonate–marl successions of Ilam, Sarvak, and Gurpi (Ki, Ks, Kg), and Jurassic–Triassic carbonate–clastic units (Jn, Js, TrJ), along with Palaeozoic basement remnants (Pz). Complete information on the formations studied is provided in Figure S1b of the supplementary material.

Fold	Δ RMSE (CT vs LGBM)	Δ MAE (CT vs LGBM)	Δ R ² (CT vs LGBM)	Δ RMSE (CT vs XGB)	Δ MAE (CT vs XGB)	Δ R ² (CT vs XGB)
1	3.347	2.926	0.381	0.465	0.483	0.032
2	1.309	0.807	0.167	1.733	1.150	0.233
3	-1.233	-0.874	-0.138	-1.139	-0.797	-0.130

Supplementary Table S3. Fold-wise pairwise performance differences used for aggregated comparison. Δ RMSE and Δ MAE were computed as (baseline – CT-TreeFlow) so that positive values indicate lower prediction error for CT-TreeFlow. Δ R² was computed as (CT-TreeFlow – baseline), where positive values indicate higher explained variance for CT-TreeFlow. Values were derived from the fold-level cross-validation metrics reported in CV_fold_metrics.csv.

Fold	Training samples	Validation samples	Test samples
1	799,975	199,969	299,997
2	799,958	199,840	300,000
3	800,000	199,907	300,000

Supplementary Table S4. Exact training, validation, and test sample counts for each spatial cross-validation fold. Sample sizes correspond to the spatial GroupKFold cross-validation partitions used during model training and evaluation. Each fold was constructed to maintain spatial independence between training, validation, and test datasets.

Supplementary Figure S3. Observed versus predicted responses for baseline tree-based models across spatial cross-validation folds. Scatter plots illustrate the relationship between observed target values and the corresponding predictions generated by the baseline machine learning models used for comparison with CT-TreeFlow. The panels summarize the predictive behaviour of LightGBM and XGBoost across the independent test partitions of the spatial cross-validation procedure.

Supplementary Figure S4. Observed versus predicted responses for the XGBoost model across spatial folds. Scatter plots show the relationship between observed responses and predictions produced by the XGBoost model on the independent test partitions for the three spatial cross-validation folds.

Supplementary Figure S5. Residual error distributions of the baseline models across spatial cross-validation folds. Histograms illustrate the distributions of prediction residuals (Observed – Predicted) computed on the independent test partitions for the baseline machine learning models used for comparison with CT-TreeFlow. The panels summarize the residual structures obtained for LightGBM and XGBoost across the three spatial cross-validation folds.

Supplementary Figure S6. Residual error distributions for the XGBoost model across spatial folds. Histograms illustrate the distributions of prediction residuals (Observed – Predicted) computed on the independent test sets for the three spatial cross-validation folds.

Fold	CRPS
Fold 1	0.121048
Fold 2	0.197989
Fold 3	0.226217
Mean	0.181751
Standard deviation (SD)	0.054124
Standard error (SE)	0.031252
95% CI (lower)	0.0479
95% CI (upper)	0.3156

Supplementary Table S5. Fold-level CRPS statistics used to derive the aggregated probabilistic performance metrics of CT-TreeFlow. The table reports the continuous ranked probability score (CRPS) values obtained for each spatial cross-validation fold based on the independent test partitions. Summary statistics including the mean, standard deviation (SD), standard error (SE), and descriptive 95% confidence interval (CI) are provided for transparency and reproducibility of the aggregated results reported in Table 4-4.

Figure S7. Spatial distribution of groundwater potential predicted by the LightGBM model across the study area based on cross-validated outputs. Groundwater potential is classified into five categories (very low, low, moderate, high, and very high). The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are overlaid for reference.

Figure S8. Spatial distribution of groundwater potential predicted by the XGBoost model across the study area based on cross-validated outputs. Groundwater potential is classified into five categories (very low, low, moderate, high, and very high). The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are overlaid for reference.

Figure S9. Spatial distribution of predictive uncertainty derived from the LightGBM model across the study area. The map represents the predictive standard deviation obtained from the probabilistic outputs of the model based on cross-validated predictions. The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are overlaid for spatial reference.

Figure S10. Spatial distribution of predictive uncertainty derived from the XGBoost model across the study area. The map represents the predictive standard deviation obtained from the probabilistic outputs of the model based on cross-validated predictions. The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are overlaid for spatial reference.

Figure S11. Spatial distribution of groundwater potential derived from the ensemble prediction of the three machine learning models (CT-TreeFlow, LightGBM, and XGBoost). The map was generated by calculating the cell-wise mean of the cross-validated spatial predictions produced by the individual models, resulting in a consensus groundwater potential surface across the study area. Groundwater potential values are classified into five categories (very low, low, moderate, high, and very high). The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are overlaid for spatial reference.

Figure S12. Spatial distribution of predictive uncertainty associated with the ensemble modelling framework. The map represents the standard deviation of the predicted groundwater potential values obtained from the three models (CT-TreeFlow, LightGBM, and XGBoost) at each grid cell, quantifying the variability among model predictions. The locations of springs (blue circles) and cave locations (black dots) are shown for reference